

Study on Antibacterial and Antioxidant Activity of Extracts from Hydroponic Pennywort Tubers (*Centella Asiatica* (L.) Urban)

Vuong Bao Thy¹, Vo Thanh Beo², Tran Huu Thanh Huy³, Bui The Vinh⁴

^{1,2,3,4} Faculty of Health Sciences, Mekong University, Vietnam

ABSTRACT: Several plant species have been found to contain bioactive compounds that contribute positively to health and are utilized across food, pharmaceutical, and cosmetic industries. The purpose of this research is to investigate the antibacterial and antioxidant activities of extracts derived from hydroponically grown pennywort tubers (*Centella asiatica* (L.) Urban). The results show that the antioxidant activity of the extract (IC₅₀) was 6.85 mg/mL. The extract demonstrates antibacterial efficacy against foodborne pathogen *Escherichiacoli* and the pathogenic bacterium *Staphylococcus aureus* at the extract concentration of 250 mg/mL. These results underscore the potential of hydroponically cultivated pennywort tubers as a source of bioactive compounds with beneficial applications in the food, pharmaceutical, and cosmetic industries. Further research is warranted to fully explore the hydroponically grown pennywort tubers, aiming to harness their medicinal attributes for disease prevention and human health enhancement in the future.

Published Online:
June 21, 2024

KEYWORDS: *Centella asiatica* (L.) Urban, hoạt tính kháng khuẩn, hoạt tính kháng oxy hóa (DPPH)

Corresponding Author:

Vuong Bao Thy

1. INTRODUCTION

The bioactive compounds found in plants offer many important benefits for current and future medical applications (Wawrosch and Zotchev, 2021). These compounds, present in foods such as vegetables, fruits, and whole grains, are essential for human health (Pai *et al.*, 2022). Because of their nutritional, health and therapeutic benefits, extensive research has been conducted on bioactive compounds for their potential applications across various fields (Huang and Chen, 2022).

Pennywort, scientifically known as *Centella asiatica* (L.) Urban, is a traditional herbal remedy used in Southeast Asia (Barge *et al.*, 2023). *Centella asiatica* is characterized by its rich content of active substances from various chemical groups, including triterpenoids, carotenoids, glycosides, flavonoids, alkaloids, essential oils, and fatty oils. These compounds exhibit antibacterial, antiviral, antioxidant, wound healing, and antidepressant effects. They aid in improving cognitive function and support the treatment of cardiovascular, gastrointestinal, diabetic, cancerous, and gynecological diseases (Wiciński *et al.*, 2024).

Recent studies consider pennywort as an antioxidant, reducing the effects of stress both in vitro and in vivo. The high antioxidant contents present in this plant suggest that it could serve as a potential alternative source of natural antioxidants (Abdul Rahim *et al.*, 2021). Moreover, pennywort has demonstrated antibacterial properties, effectively resist bacteria that cause disease and food poisoning (Norzaharaini *et al.*, 2011; Pitinidhipat and Yasurin 2012).

Studies conducted in the world and in Vietnam have focused on chemical composition and biological activity of pennywort (Seevaratnam *et al.*, 2012) as well as exploring the pharmacological application of pennywort leaves in the production of commercial products (Ploenkutham *et al.*, 2018; Chuthaputti, 2011). However, research on potential bioactive compounds of pennywort tubers is still limited. Hence, this study aims to determine the antibacterial and antioxidant activities of extracts derived from hydroponic pennywort tubers (*Centella asiatica* (L.) Urban). This investigation serves as a basis for in-depth research on pennywort tubers for potential applications in food, pharmaceuticals, and cosmetics production in the future.

Vuong Bao Thy et al, Study on Antibacterial and Antioxidant Activity of Extracts from Hydroponic Pennywort Tubers (*Centella Asiatica* (L.) Urban)

2. MATERIAL AND METHODS

2.1 Plant material

Hydroponically grown pennywort tubers were collected from Hoang Long Farm - BC Vu Long Company Limited in Village 4, MyLong commune, CaoLanh district, DongThap province. These tubers were typically harvested 6 months after planting. The tubers were transported to the processing area where they underwent sorting to remove damaged and rotten tubers. The substrate was cleaned and fluffed before the tubers were further processed. A thorough rinse within water lasting 3-5 minutes was conducted, followed by draining for approximately 30 minutes.

2.2 Methods

2.2.1 Sample preparation

Centella asiatica tubers were extracted according to the research of Kumar and Kavita (2020) with modifications. 50.0 g of hydroponic pennywort root were used to remove the roots, wash, and cut into pieces of 0.5-1.0 cm, and mince with extraction solvent (ratio 1:1, w/ v) to obtain a mixture. Remove solvent from the mixture using a rotary vacuum evaporator. The collected mixture was filtered through Whatman filter paper No. 4 (hole size 20-25 μm) and then centrifuged at 6000 rpm to collect the extract. The used solvent was Ethanol 60%. The control solvent was distilled water.

2.2.2 Measurement of antioxidant activity

Antioxidant activity of hydroponic pennywort tuber extract was performed by the DPPH (2,2-diphenyl-1-picryl hydrazyl) radical scavenging activity measurement (Ye *et al.*, 2013) with modifications. 200 μL of the extract (with different concentrations) was dissolved in 1 mL of 0.1 mM DPPH and then shaken well to obtain a reaction mixture. The reaction mixture was incubated in the dark at 30 °C for 30 minutes, and then was measured absorbance at 517 nm using UV/Vis Spectrophotometer. Vitamin C (ascorbic acid) was used as positive control. The experiment was repeated 3 times.

The DPPH inhibition ability was calculated according to the following formula:

$$\%I = \left(1 - \frac{A_{\text{sample}}}{A_0}\right) \times 100$$

Note: %I: % of antioxidant activity.

A_0 : Control reaction absorbance

A_{sample} : Testing specimen absorbance

The control solution (vitamin C) was prepared stock at a concentration of 1 mg/mL (1000 ppm) in ethanol, and then was diluted 100 times to obtain a concentration of 10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ (10 ppm). Dilution of vitamin C solutions from initial concentration of 10 ppm to obtain a vitamin C solution concentration of 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, and 10 ppm.

Add 1 mL of diluted vitamin C to 1 mL of 0.1 mM (DPPH) in ethanol 95%. The mixture was mixed and left for 30 min at room temperature in the dark. The absorbance of the reaction mixture was measured at 517 nm by using a UV-VIS spectrophotometer. A standard curve is established $y = ax + b$ with the percentage of DPPH inhibition at different concentrations. And then, the IC_{50} value of vitamin C and hydroponic pennywort extract were calculated.

2.2.3 Antibacterial activity testing

Evaluation of antibacterial activity of hydroponic pennywort tuber extract was determined according to the study of Mythili *et al* (2012) with modifications. *Escherichia coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus* were cultured on LB media (Luria Bertani) at 37°C for 24 hours. Transfer bacterial colonies to 4 mL of LB media and then shake overnight at 37°C. The extract was made different concentrations (250, 500, and 1000 mg/mL). The positive control was Ampicillin (100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$). Dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) 30% was as the negative control.

The activity test plate was prepared by spreading 100 μL of bacterial solution (10^6 CFU/mL) onto the surface of LB agar, let it dry for 15 minutes, and made holes in the agar surface with a diameter of 6 mm (agar wells). Add 50 μL of the diluted extract at different concentrations (or control) into the prepared agar wells, and then the plate were incubated for 24 hours at 37°C. Measure the diameter of the antibacterial ring after 24 hours, each experiment repeated 3 times. The diameter of the antibacterial rings were determined by the formula: $H = D - d$ (mm), in which: D was the antibacterial ring's diameter calculated from the central's hole (mm); d was the agar hole's diameter (mm). Antibacterial ability was measured as following: no antibacterial activity (<1 mm), weak antibacterial activity (1 – 5 mm), moderate antibacterial activity (1 - 20mm), strong antibacterial activity (>20 mm).

Figure 1: Diagram of injecting extract, positive control, and negative control into agar wells at different treatment concentrations

Note: 1, 2, 3: concentrations of diluted extract; (+): Positive control – Ampicillin 100 µg/mL ; (-): Negative control – DMSO 30 %.

2.2.4 Statistical analysis

Excel 2016 software and Statgraphics XIX software were used to analyze variance (ANOVA), standard deviation (SD), and LSD test.

3. RESULTS

3.1 Antioxidant activity of hydroponic pennywort tuber extract

Table 1 presents the DPPH (2,2-diphenyl-1-picryl hydrazyl) radical scavenging activity of hydroponic pennywort tuber extract. The results show a linear increase in DPPH free radical removal efficiency of the extract concentration. In particular, the concentration of the extract rose from 1mg/mL to 10mg/mL, the free radical removal efficiency increased from 24% to 65%. Notably, the DPPH free radical removal efficiency at concentration of 10 mg/mL was the highest and significantly different from other concentrations ($p < 0.05$).

The IC₅₀ value of hydroponic pennywort tuber extract was analyzed and presented in Table 1. The lower IC₅₀ value indicates higher antioxidant activity. The IC₅₀ value of hydroponic pennywort extract was 6.85 mg/mL and the IC₅₀ of vitamin C (6.12 µg/mL) displayed the antioxidant activity of hydroponic pennywort extract was lower than the antioxidant activity of vitamin C.

Table 1: DPPH free radical scavenging activity of the extract and vitamin C

Hydroponic pennywort extract		Vitamin C	
Concentration (mg/mL)	DPPH activity * (%)	Concentration (µg/ml)	DPPH activity * (%)
1	24.96 ⁱ ± 1.53	1	8.87 ^j ± 1.10
2	28.59 ^h ± 0.90	2	16.47 ⁱ ± 1.16
3	31.80 ^g ± 1.66	3	24.94 ^h ± 0.84
4	35.95 ^f ± 1.05	4	33.63 ^g ± 0.71
5	39.29 ^e ± 1.16	5	41.01 ^f ± 0.94
6	46.86 ^d ± 2.49	6	49.38 ^e ± 0.88
7	49.02 ^d ± 1.29	7	57.07 ^d ± 1.00
8	54.89 ^c ± 2.16	8	68.44 ^c ± 0.86
9	61.69 ^b ± 0.98	9	73.14 ^b ± 1.11
10	65.71 ^a ± 1.60	10	78.14 ^a ± 0.88
Regression equation: $y = 5.45x + 12.63$ ($R^2 = 0.93$)		Regression equation: $y = 8.03x + 0.84$ ($R^2 = 0.99$)	
IC ₅₀ = 6.85 mg/mL		IC ₅₀ = 6.12 (µg/mL)	

(*) The values were the average values of three repetitions. In the same column, values followed by a different letter represent statistically significant differences ($p < 0.05$).

Polyphenol and flavonoid compounds in pennywort were the main ingredients with antioxidant properties (Jhansi and Kola (2019). According to the study of Pittella (2009), the extract from pennywort leaves had the ability to remove DPPH free radicals and the IC₅₀ value was 31.25 µg/mL, while the IC₅₀ of vitamin C) was 2.50 µg/mL.

Vuong Bao Thy et al, Study on Antibacterial and Antioxidant Activity of Extracts from Hydroponic Pennywort Tubers (Centella Asiatica (L.) Urban)

3.2 Antibacterial activities of hydroponic pennywort tuber extract for Escherichia coli and Staphylococcus aureus

Antibacterial activities of *Escherichia coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus* of hydroponic pennywort tuber were investigated and evaluated by the diameter of the antibacterial rings. The appearance of antibacterial rings around the wells in the agar plate is due to the antibacterial active substances of the extract diffused from the center of the wells to the surrounding wells and inhibited the growth of bacteria.

The results depicted in Figure 2 show that the extract derived from the hydroponic pennywort tuber extracts (samples extracted with ethanol: A and C) exhibited antibacterial activity against *Escherichia coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus*. Meanwhile, samples extracted with water (B and D) did not demonstrate corresponding antibacterial properties. The size of the sterile zone diameter correlates with the antimicrobial activity resulting from the extraction process, while smaller diameters suggest weaker antimicrobial effects.

Figure 2: Antibacterial rings of the hydroponic pennywort tuber extract for Escherichia coli and Staphylococcus aureus
 A, B – Antibacterial ability for *Escherichia coli* of samples extracted with ethanol and water at different concentrations (250 mg/mL, 500 mg/mL, and 1000 mg/mL).
 C, D – Antibacterial ability for *Staphylococcus aureus* of samples extracted with ethanol and water at different concentrations 250 mg/mL, 500 mg/mL, and 1000 mg/mL.
 (+) the positive control, Ampicillin 100 µg/mL.
 (-) the negative control, DMSO 30%.

Table 2: Antibacterial ring’s diameters of Escherichia coli and Staphylococcus aureus of the hydroponic pennywort tuber extracts

Extract concentration	Antibacterial ring’s diameter for <i>E. coli</i> * (mm)	Antibacterial ring’s diameter for <i>S. aureus</i> * (mm)
250 mg/mL	7.33 ^b ± 1.53	8.00 ^c ± 1.00
500 mg/mL	9.67 ^b ± 2.08	10.67 ^b ± 0.58
1000 mg/mL	12.67 ^a ± 0.58	14.33 ^a ± 1.15
Ampicillin 100 µg/mL	14.33 ^a ± 1.15	15.67 ^a ± 1.53
CV%	27.95	27.11

(*): the average value of three repetitions.
 Negative control: DMSO 30%. Positive control: Ampicillin 100 µg/mL.

Table 2 shows that the extract concentrations at/or more than 250 mg/mL had the ability to fight against *Escherichia coli*. The extract’s antibacterial ability at a concentration of 1000 mg/mL (12.67 ± 0,58 mm) was outstanding compared to other concentrations (250 mg/mL – 7.33 ± 1,53 mm and 500 mg/mL - 9,67 ± 2,08 mm) and lower than the positive control Ampicillin 100 µg/mL (14.33^a ± 1.15 mm), no statistically significant difference ($p > 0.05$).

For *Staphylococcus aureus* (Table 2), the extract displayed the antibacterial activities for all the extract concentrations and the antibacterial ring’s diameter values were statistically significant difference ($p > 0.05$). The extract at a concentration of 1000 mg/mL showed the highest antibacterial ability, the antibacterial ring’s diameter of 14.33 ± 1,15 mm. The antibacterial ability of the extract for *Staphylococcus aureus* was lower than the positive control (Ampicillin 100 µg/mL, the ring’s diameter of 15,67 ± 1,53 mm) and no statistically significant difference ($p > 0.05$).

According to the study of Mamtha *et al* (2004), the antibacterial properties of Indian pennywort leaf extract could fight bacteria that cause intestinal diseases. The minimum concentration to inhibit *Escherichia coli* (with an antibacterial ring’s diameter of 15 – 20 mm) was 100mg/mL; and for *taphylococcus aureus* at the minimum concentration (with an antibacterial ring’s diameter of less than 15 mm) was 100mg/mL.

Vuong Bao Thy et al, Study on Antibacterial and Antioxidant Activity of Extracts from Hydroponic Pennywort Tubers (*Centella Asiatica* (L.) Urban)

Extracts from the leaves and roots of pennywort had the antibacterial effects for pathogenic bacteria. Using ethanol solvent to extract compounds from the pennywort had higher efficiency than chloroform and water. The minimum inhibitory concentration for *Escherichia coli* was 2.5 mg/mL and for *Staphylococcus aureus* was 5.0 mg/mL (Nasution *et al.*, 2018).

The antibacterial activity of pennywort extract was attributed to the compounds such as alkaloids, cardiac glycosides, saponins, tannins, flavonoids, terpenoids, and phenols, that inhibit Gram-negative bacteria such as *Escherichia coli*, *Vibrio cholera*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Samolnella senftenberg*, *Shigella dysenteriae* and Gram-positive bacteria such as *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Streptococcus mutans*, *Streptococcus pneumoniae*, *Bacillus anthracis*, and *Bacillus subtilis*. Therefore, the pennywort extract could be used as a substitute for tetracycline (Sieber *et al.*, 2020).

4. CONCLUSION

The study has identified the antibacterial and antioxidant activities of extracts derived from hydroponic pennywort tuber (*Centella asiatica* (L.) Urban). The the extract (IC₅₀) demonstrated an antioxidant activity with an IC value of 6.85 mg/mL. The extract also exhibited efficacy against foodborne bacteria such as *Escherichia coli* and pathogenic bacteria - *Staphylococcus aureus* at a concentration of 250 mg/mL. The results show that the hydroponic pennywort tuber extract may contain bioactive compounds. Given these potential results, it is necessary to conduct further research on hydroponically grown pennywort tubers. This research could lead to development of new applications in food, pharmaceutical, and cosmetic fields, making the most of its valuable medicinal properties of pennywort to create high-value products.

REFERENCES

1. Abdul Rahim, MSA, Baharudin, NA, Ahmad Nazri, IA et al (2021). "Effect of different drying methods on the antioxidant properties of leaves of *Centella asiatica* ", *IOP Conf. Series: Earth and Environmental Science*, 756: 012054. DOI: 10.1088/1755-1315/756/1/012054 .
2. Barge, S., Jade, D., Talukdar, NC (2023). "Centella asiatica Linn", *Potent Anticancer Medicinal Plants* , 1st Edition, Pages 19. eBook: ISBN 9781003431190.
3. Chuthaputti, A. (2011) "Asiatic penny wort (Buabok) - herb of the year", *Journal of Traditional Thai and Alternative Medicine*, Vol. 9, No. 2, 84-93.
4. Huang W., Chen L. (2022) . "Emerging sources and applications of alternative proteins: An introduction ", *Advances in Food and Nutrition Research* , 101, 237-275 . DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/bs.afnr.2022.05.003> .
5. Jhansi, D., and Kola, M. (2019). "The antioxidant potential of *Centella asiatica*", *Journal of Medical Plant Studies*, 7(2), 18-20.
6. Kumar, J. P. and Kavita, T. (2020). "Isolation and Phytochemical analysis of Terpenoids and Asiaticosides from *Centella asiatica* for their neuroprotective activities", *Research Journal of Chemistry and Environment* , 24(3).
7. Mamtha, B, Kavitha, K., Srinivasan, K. K. et al (2004). "An in vitro study of the effect of *Centella asiatica* [Indian pennywort] on enteric pathogens", *Indian Journal of Pharmacology* , 36(1): 41.
8. Mythili, T., and Ravindhran, R. (2012). "Phytochemical screening and antimicrobial activity of *Sesbania sesban* (L.) Merr", *Asian Journal of Pharmaceutical and Clinical Research*, Vol 5, Issue 4.
9. Nasution, M.Y., Restuati, M., Pulungan, A.S.S. et al (2018). "Antimicrobial activities of *Centella asiatica* leaf and root extracts on selected pathogenic microorganisms ", *Journal of Medical Sciences* , 18(4), 198-204. DOI: 10.3923/jms.2018.198.204 .
10. Norzaharaini, M., Norshazwani, W. S, Hasmah, A. et al (2011). "A preliminary study on the antimicrobial activities of asiaticoside and asiatic acid against selected gram positive and gram negative bacteria ", *Health Environ J*, 2(1): 23–26 .
11. Pai S. , Hebbar A. , Selvaraj S . (2022) . "A critical look at challenges and future scopes of bioactive compounds and their incorporations in the food, energy, and pharmaceutical sector ", *Environmental Science Pollution Research International* , 29 (24): 35518–35541 . DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-022-19423-4> .
12. Pitinidhipat, N. and Yasurin, P. (2012). "Antibacterial Activity of *Chrysanthemum indicum*, *Centella asiatica* and *Andrographis paniculata* on *Bacillus cereus* and *Listeria monocytogenes* under Osmotic Stress . *AU JT*, 2012; 15(4): 239-245.
13. Pittella, F., Dutra, R.C., Junior, DD et al (2009). "Antioxidant and Cytotoxic Activities of *Centella asiatica* (L) Urb", *Int. J. Mol. Sci* , (10): 3713-3721. DOI: 10.3390/ijms10093713 .
14. Ploenkutham, R., Sripromma , P., Amornraksa , S. et al (2018). "Effect of Roasting and Kneading on Antioxidant Activity and Consumer Acceptance towards Asiatic Pennywort Tea ", *MATEC Web Conf* , Volume 187 . DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1051/mateconf/201818701004> .
15. Seevaratnam , V., Banumathi , P., Premalatha , M.R. . et al (2012) . "Functional properties of *Centella asiatica* (L.): a review ", *Int. J. Pharm. Pharm. Sci* . 4 (5): 8–14.

Vuong Bao Thy et al, Study on Antibacterial and Antioxidant Activity of Extracts from Hydroponic Pennywort Tubers (*Centella Asiatica* (L.) Urban)

16. Sieberi, BM, Omwenga, GI, Wambua, RK et al (2020). "Screening of the Dichloromethane: Methanolic Extract of *Centella asiatica* for Antibacterial Activities against *Salmonella typhi*, *Escherichia coli*, *Shigella sonnei*, *Bacillus subtilis*, and *Staphylococcus aureus* ", *Scientific World Journal* , vol. 2020, Article ID 6378712, 8 pages. DOI: 10.1155/2020/6378712 .
17. Wawrosch C. and Zotchev S. B. (2021). “ Production of bioactive plant secondary metabolites through in vitro technologies—status and outlook ”, *Applied Microbiology and Biotechnology* , 105 (18): 6649–6668. Doi: 10.1007/s00253-021-11539-w.
18. Wiciński, M., Fajkiel-Madajczyk, A, Kurant, Z., et al (2024). "Can Asiatic Acid from *Centella asiatica* be a Potential Remedy in Cancer Therapy? - A Review", *Cancers*, 16(7), 1317. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3390/cancers16071317> .
19. Ye, M., Ren, L., Wu, Y. et al (2013). “Quality characteristics and antioxidant activity of hickory black soybean yogurt”, *LWT-Food Science and Technology*, (51): 314-318. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lwt.2012.09.027> .